

Amplified restriction fragments for genomic enrichment

(version 2.6 July 2014)

Tom Parchman (tparchma@uwyo.edu)
Zach Gompert (zgompert@uwyo.edu)
Liz Mandeville (emandevi@uwyo.edu)
Alex Buerkle (buerkle@uwyo.edu)
University of Wyoming

This is a protocol for preparing highly-multiplexed samples for high-throughput sequencing. Genomic DNA is digested with restriction enzymes, barcodes and Illumina adaptor sequences are ligated to the digested fragments, and a subset of these fragments is amplified by PCR. Amplified fragments are purified and size-selected in agarose before being pooled into an Illumina sequencing library (see Fig. 2). This is a flexible protocol that has worked with a wide variety of taxa and can be modified to target a variable number of fragments for sequencing (see Fig. 3). This protocol is used and described in detail by Parchman *et al.* (2012).

Disclaimer: We cannot guarantee your success with this protocol. We also caution that this protocol and other approaches to multiplexed sequencing lead to immense amounts of data, with stochastic variation in sequence coverage across individuals and genetic regions. Importantly, we recommend making a comprehensive plan for analyzing the data before you follow this protocol. If you do not know what you will do with $> 10^8$ barcoded sequencing reads, then this protocol will not be useful.

1 Reagents and Equipment

1. EcoRI (NEB, 20,000 units/mL) R0101L
2. MseI (NEB, 10,000 units/mL) R0525L
3. T4 DNA ligase (NEB, 400,000 units/mL) M0202L
4. BioRad Iproof High Fidelity DNA polymerase Cat no. 172-5301 (\$424 for 250 μ L [500 units])
5. 1 mg/mL BSA
6. 1 M NaCl
7. DMSO
8. EcoRI adaptors (see below)
9. MseI adaptors (see below)
10. Thermal Cyclers (2)
11. 96 well plates and strip caps
12. Full plate centrifuge
13. Nanodrop or similar spectrophotometer
14. other reagents listed below

1.1 Items only needed if doing Gel Purification

1. Molecular Biology grade agarose (suggestion: BioRad 161-3101)
2. QIAquick gel extraction kit Cat no. 28706(\$464 for 250)
3. Agarose gel rig
4. UV light table and UV face shields

2 Oligonucleotide Sequences

2.1 Adaptors

2.1.1 EcoRI

1. See Table S1 for barcoded EcoRI primer combinations. These adaptor sequences come in pairs and after annealing become one double-stranded adaptor. The barcodes residing in the adaptors were created using python scripts described in (Meyer & Kircher, 2010). To create variability in the initial bases for Illumina sequencing, we created barcodes that were 8, 9, and 10 bases in length. We constructed sets of barcodes so that all barcodes differ by a minimum of 4 bases. This facilitates correction of sequencing errors in barcodes. From the total set, we used an additional python script to select a subset that is balanced in the usage of nucleotides at each position. Further information on the python scripts can be found at (<http://bioinf.eva.mpg.de/multiplex/>).
2. Mix 1 μL of each oligo in a pair (100 μM stock) with 98 μL of water to make 100 μL of 1 pmole/ μL (1 μM) of annealed, double-stranded adaptor stock. Heat to 95°C for 5 minutes and slowly cool to room temperature. This annealing step only needs to be performed once for a stock solution of adaptor. Keep the set of adaptors organized in plate format that is convenient for later use in setting up reactions (e.g., Fig. 1).

2.1.2 MseI

Mix 10 μL of the MseI1 and MseI2 oligos (100 μM stock) with 80 μL of water to make 100 μL of 10 pmol/ μL (10 μM) stock. Heat to 95°C for 5 minutes and slowly cool to room temp to anneal oligos into double-stranded adaptor. This annealing step only needs to be performed once for a stock solution of adaptor.

These oligos are the same for each fragment. On an Illumina sequencer and with our configuration of the sequencing primer, sequencing only occurs from the EcoRI side, so there is no need to barcode the MseI oligos.

MseI1: 5' GCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGCTCTTCCGATCTG 3'

MseI2: 5' TACAGATCGGAAGAGCTCGTATGCCGTCTTCTGCTTG 3'

2.1.3 PCR primers

Mix 5 μL of the Illpcr1 and Illpcr2 oligos (100 μM stock) with 90 μL of water to make a working solution (2.5 μM of each oligo).

The asterisks between the first three bases in each PCR primer represent phosphothiolation (this is an option when ordering oligos). This prevents exonucleases from acting on the ends of the fragments, and thus protects the product prior to sequencing.

The last base of the Illpcr2 primer is a selective base and is arbitrarily **G**. Different and additional selective bases could be added, as desired. However, there is some evidence that the selective base does not function with high-fidelity polymerase and could be omitted.

Illpcr1 (Forward): 5' A*A*TGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACACTCTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCT 3'

Selective Illpcr2 (Reverse): 5' C*A*AGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGCTCTTCCGATCTGTAAG 3'

Figure 1: Sample layouts of 96 adaptor oligos on plates. At left are plates as they would be ordered. Oligos pairs are combined, annealed and then stored for use as in the plate on the right.

2.1.4 Illumina sequencing primer

This primer is used during Illumina sequencing, is not part of the library prep, and is presented here only to document its sequence.

5' `ACACTCTTTCCTACACGACGCTCTTCGGATC` 3'

3 Restriction and Ligation Reactions

Genomic DNA is first digested with two restriction enzymes, EcoRI and MseI. This results in a pool of fragments that have the sticky-ended restriction cut sites on either end, and these ends provide a template for ligation of the customized adaptor sequences. The adaptor sequences contain the Illumina adaptors and primer sequences (and hence provide a binding site for the Illumina PCR primers). After the Illumina adaptor sequences on the EcoRI end, 8–10 base pair barcodes are incorporated that allow the identification of the origin of each sequencing read. The five bases at the 3' end of each adaptor oligo correspond to the ligation site; that is, they match the restriction cut site and have one added, protector base that prevents the cut from occurring again. The restriction digest is run first, followed by the permanent inactivation of enzymes by heating to 65°C. The ligation reaction is then run separately, so digestion of adaptors containing restriction enzyme cut sites cannot occur (a small number of our 768 EcoRI adaptor sequences contain the EcoRI or MseI cut sites; likewise for any other potential alternative restriction enzymes) and reactions can occur at their optimum temperatures.

3.1 Restriction Digest

1. Place 6 μL of sample DNA in each well of a plate (DNA should ideally be at a minimum concentration of 20 $\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$ and a maximum concentration of 150 $\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$ (note: this is for small

genomes, for large genomes add higher concentrations of DNA). Keep on ice.

2. For each sample prepare master mix I (Table 1), mix by vortexing, and centrifuge.
For these and all other reactions make sure to prepare an excess of mix to accommodate multiple rounds of pipetting, particularly if you are working with whole plates. Because the enzymes are stored in glycerol and other viscous solutions, a substantial volume is lost through adhesion to the outside of pipette tips. We suggest making 150% of what you think you will need.
3. Add 3 μL of the combined master mix I to each sample. Always keep cold once the enzymes have been added.
4. The total reaction volume should be 9 μL . Cover and seal the plate, vortex, centrifuge and incubate at 37 °C for 8 hours, followed by 65°C for 45 minutes (to inactivate the enzyme) on a thermalcycler with a heated lid.

Reagent	Number of samples 1×
10× T4 Buffer	1.15
1M NaCl	0.60
1 mg/mL BSA	0.60
Water	0.25
MseI	0.12
EcoRI	0.28

Table 1: Reagents and volumes for Restriction Digest master mix I (3 μL prepared per sample).

3.2 Adaptor Ligation

1. Thaw MseI and EcoRI adaptors. Have these adaptors annealed and easily accessible in plate format (for the EcoRI adaptors) (see Sections 2.1.1 and 2.1.2).
2. Add 1.4 μL of master mix II to each restriction-digested reaction.
3. Add 1 μL of EcoRI adaptors to each well on plate. Note that the MseI adaptor is in master mix I.
4. The total reaction volume should now be 11.4 μL . Cover and seal the plate, vortex, centrifuge and incubate at 16 °C for 6 hours on a thermalcycler.
5. Dilute the Restriction-Ligation reaction with 189 μL of 0.1× TE. Store at 4 °C for a month, or -20 °C for longer.

Reagent	Number of samples 1×
MseI adaptor	1
Water	0.072
10× T4 buffer	0.1
1M NaCl	0.05
1 mg/mL BSA	0.05
T4 DNA ligase	0.1675

Table 2: Reagents and volumes for Restriction-Ligation master mix II (1.4 μ L prepared per sample).

4 PCR amplification

1. This PCR step uses the Illumina PCR primers to amplify fragments that have our adaptors+barcodes ligated onto the ends. To ameliorate stochastic differences in PCR production of fragments in reactions, we run two separate 20 μ L reactions per restriction-ligation product, and later combine them.

Restriction-Ligation products may be pooled prior to PCR for projects with large numbers of individuals, with up to 768 individuals per reaction (corresponding to the total number of unique EcoRI adaptors, or “barcodes”). Following Ligation, each individual is uniquely labeled, so pooling for PCR will not introduce contamination. In this pooling scheme, all individuals intended for a single lane of Illumina sequencing are pooled following Ligation, so each individual is present in each of 96 wells x 2 replicates = 192 reactions. There are two advantages to pooling restriction-ligation products prior to PCR: 1) amplification is potentially more consistent across individuals, and 2) pooling reduces both time in the lab and use of costly Iproof taq polymerase.

Reagent	20 μ L Reaction	40 μ L Reaction
Water	9.67	19.33
5× Iproof buffer	4.0	7.99
dNTP (10 mM)	0.4	0.8
MgCl ₂ (50mM)	0.4	0.8
Pre-mixed PCR Primers, 5 μ M	1.33	2.66
Iproof taq	0.2	0.4
DMSO	0.15	0.30
R/L product	4	8

Table 3: Reagents and volumes for PCR amplification reactions.

2. Thermalcycler profile for this PCR: 98°C for 30s; 30 cycles of: 98°C for 20s, 60°C for 30s, 72°C for 40s; final extension at 72°C for 10 min.

5 Extra PCR step

1. This PCR step adds Illumina PCR primers, dNTPs, and iproof buffer and executes a final long PCR cycle. The purpose of this step is to attempt to convert single stranded template remaining from the first PCR to double stranded. This typically results in libraries that have a better distribution of fragments in the correct size range, presumably because it removes single stranded molecules that interfere with the precision of the electrophoresis step below.
2. Add 2.125 μL of the mix below directly to each reaction immediately after the PCR step above is completed.

Reagent	20 μL Reaction
5 \times Iproof buffer	0.425
dNTP (10 mM)	0.4
Pre-mixed PCR Primers, 5 μM	1.33

Table 4: Reagents and volumes for PCR optional final PCR cycle.

3. Thermalcycler profile for this PCR cycle: 98°C for 3 min; 60°C for 2 mins, and 72°C for 10 min.
4. Note that we are still in the process of determining empirically how well this extra step works.

6 Blue Pippin size selection (Option 1, preferred)

This step reduces the template for sequencing by selecting a desired size range of DNA fragments, and is usually done by the sequencing facility. Note that this step replaces Gel Purification as our preferred method for size-selection of DNA fragments for the final sequencing library. We prefer Blue Pippin for two reasons. First, Bioanalyzer results suggest that Blue Pippin achieves cleaner size selection. Second, Blue Pippin is more reproducible than the Gel Purification methods that we previously used.

Blue Pippin works in a similar way to typical gel electrophoresis, but uses standardized gel cassettes and automated size selection, rather than a hand-poured gel and manual excision of fragments from a gel. It is necessary to specify a size range of fragments that you would like represented in the final genomic library for sequencing. The target size range can be adjusted to modify the number of fragments expected for sequencing. Because techniques such as this typically result in a negative relationship between fragment size and number, selecting larger fragments should decrease the final number of fragments in the template and increase the coverage depth of these regions after sequencing. Similarly, decreasing the size interval selected will also reduce the number of fragments and increase coverage. The number of fragments produced is also in part a function of genome size, so awareness of your organism’s genome size is helpful in making an appropriate choice for size selection (Fig. 3). We have typically used a 50–100 bp range somewhere between 250 and 500 bp in total fragment length (meaning that we might select, as an example, fragments that are 300–400 bp in length).

7 Gel Purification size selection (Option 2)

This step involves cutting a desired size range of fragments out of an agarose gel. The size range cut out of the gel can be adjusted to modify the number of fragments expected for sequencing. Because techniques such as this typically result in a negative relationship between fragment size and number, cutting out larger fragments should decrease the final number of fragments in the template and increase the coverage depth of these regions after sequencing. To eliminate variation in the size and amount of agarose punched out for each sample, it is recommended to pool all PCR reactions (they already have the barcodes incorporated) before loading the gel. The pooled library can then be run in as many wells on the gel as necessary. We are running 96 samples in replicate on two plates, pooling all of the PCR product, and then running approximately 10 lanes on a single agarose gel. If desired, allowing PCR product to evaporate on the bench top for several hours (or overnight) concentrates the PCR product, and means that fewer lanes are required on the gel to accommodate all of the samples (however, note that gels can be overloaded with concentrated DNA and lead to anomalous migration in the gel).

1. Run the PCR product out on 2.5% agarose gel at 100 volts for 2–3 hours (adjust voltage and time as needed for different gel boxes). It is important to include a good 100 bp or 50 bp ladder at multiple spots on the gel so that a clear line can be visualized across the gel at a consistent size. Adding ethidium bromide into the gel (rather than staining after electrophoresis) reduces time and can improve consistency, and will not interfere with PCR after gel purification. We have been adding 9 μL of ethidium bromide per 200 mL of prepared gel. Be very careful that every gel is standardized as much as possible (same voltage, time, agarose concentration, etc.) in the case that multiple gels are prepped for a single library or project. This is necessary to ensure that the same size range is cut on every gel. Because PCR product can be entirely pooled for a given library, the most efficient way to proceed is to run 8–10 lanes of the pooled library on a thick gel, so 70–80 μL can be loaded into each well. This results in sufficient final library concentration and volume for Illumina sequencing (with ample excess).
2. Cut the desired region out of the gel using the large end of sterile 1000 μL pipette tips. The region between 300–400 bp seems to be a good choice here and is recommended. Because of the potentially large amount of sequence representing Illumina PCR primers in the products, cut out fragments that are at least 250 bases in length. Because cutting out regions of a gel can take some time, be sure to use face and eye UV protection. In addition, realize that long periods of UV exposure to the DNA in the gel will have a mutagenizing effect. Therefore, minimize the amount of time that the gel is exposed to the UV.
3. Purify the excised gel punches using Qiaquick gel purification kits.

8 Preparing final template for Illumina sequencing

8.1 If using Blue Pippin

For Blue Pippin, you will submit pooled PCR product without any further modification. Prior to shipping, check the concentration of the PCR product using a Nanodrop or similar spectrophotometer. DNA concentrations in PCR product are high (we have seen concentrations of 300-700

ng/ μ L using this protocol). Sequencing facilities typically request no more than 500 μ L (UT-GSAF requests 100 μ L). We recommend shipping libraries overnight on dry ice, in Safelock vials wrapped tightly in parafilm. Different sequencing facilities have different shipping preferences, so be sure to check specific requirements before shipping.

8.2 If using Gel Purification

Use a Nanodrop or similar spectrophotometer to measure the DNA concentration of purified gel punch. Add the same amount of DNA from each gel purification to a 2 mL tube. A total concentration of 25 μ L/ng – 100 μ L/ng is ideal for sending off for Illumina sequencing, although library size requirements vary. We are taking 10–50 μ L from each of the 10 purified gel punches and combining this into a pool to submit for sequencing. NCGR does not want to handle more than 500 μ L, so submit samples in 500 μ L tubes.

References

- Meyer M, Kircher M (2010) Illumina sequencing library preparation for highly multiplexed target capture and sequencing. *Cold Spring Harbor Protocols*, **2010**, pdb.prot5448.
- Parchman TL, Gompert Z, Mudge J, Schilkey F, Benkman CW, Buerkle CA (2012) Genome-wide association genetics of an adaptive trait in lodgepole pine. *Molecular Ecology*, **21**, 2991–3005.

Figure 3: Number of fragments (200–500 bp) that are expected to be generated by digesting genomes of differing size. These expectations were derived by using Perl to digest reference genomes for *Drosophila*, chicken, mouse, *Arabidopsis*, *Tribolium* and human, and to count fragments within the 200–500 bp size range. In practice, a larger number of fragments is recovered and assembled in population studies.

Table S1: Example EcoRI adaptor sequences with barcodes added. The barcodes (in uppercase letters) are located between the adaptor sequence and the restriction site sequence (see Fig. 2). The full list of barcodes can be found in the supplemental file `annealed_barcode_out_768.csv`

Name	Sequence (5' to 3')
Mid1.1	ctctttccctacacgacgctcttccgatctACGAGTGCGTc
MID1.2	aattgACGCACTCGTtagatcggaagagcgtcgtgtagggaaagagtgt
MID2.1	ctctttccctacacgacgctcttccgatctACGCTCGACAc
MID2.2	aattgTGTCGAGCGTtagatcggaagagcgtcgtgtagggaaagagtgt
MID3.1	ctctttccctacacgacgctcttccgatctAGACGCACTCc
MID3.2	aattgGAGTGCGTCTtagatcggaagagcgtcgtgtagggaaagagtgt
MID4.1	ctctttccctacacgacgctcttccgatctAGCACTGTAGc
MID4.2	aattgCTACAGTGCTtagatcggaagagcgtcgtgtagggaaagagtgt
MID6.1	ctctttccctacacgacgctcttccgatctATATCGCGAGc
MID6.2	aattgCTCGGATATtagatcggaagagcgtcgtgtagggaaagagtgt
MID7.1	ctctttccctacacgacgctcttccgatctCGTGTCTCTAc

Name	Sequence (5' to 3')
MID7.2	aattgTAGAGACACGagatcggagagcgtcgtgtagggaaagagtgt
MID8.1	ctctttccctacacgacgctcttccgatctCTCGGTGTCc
MID8.2	aattgGACACGCGAGagatcggagagcgtcgtgtagggaaagagtgt
MID10.1	ctctttccctacacgacgctcttccgatctTCTCTATGCGc
MID10.2	aattgCGCATAGAGAagatcggagagcgtcgtgtagggaaagagtgt